

Health services in the context of Third Age Tourism: Expectations and Service Satisfaction of Older Tourists

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Abstract

Objective: Third age tourism, a subset of health tourism, is gaining importance with the rise of the elderly population, which poses challenges in healthcare provision. Countries offering affordable treatment and care have facilitated the growth of this tourism segment. This study aims to provide a scientific basis for future research by examining academic publications related to health services and elderly tourist satisfaction within third age tourism using bibliometric analysis.

Materials and Methods: A search was conducted in the WOS database using keywords including "older tourists," "health services," "expectations," "satisfaction," "health tourism," and "medical tourism" for publications up to March 15, 2025. A total of 125 interdisciplinary studies were identified and analyzed using VOSviewer 1.6.18 and Microsoft Excel. Analyses included publication year trends, citation counts, countries of origin, institutions involved, and major funding organizations. **Findings:** The first relevant study was published in 2010. A decline in publication numbers occurred after 2014, 2018, and 2022, with fluctuating annual output since 2013. "Medical tourism" was the most frequent keyword (f=156), and Malaysia led in publication count (n=15). The most cited article was by Han and Hyun (2015), with 362 citations. Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT) was the top funding body, while University Sains Malaysia was the most active and well-funded institution. **Conclusion:** Third age tourism is increasingly significant due to the aging population's healthcare needs. The growing academic interest reflects this trend. The findings offer valuable insights for researchers aiming to explore elderly satisfaction and healthcare services in this context.

Keywords: Health tourism, Third age tourism, Health service satisfaction, Bibliometric analysis.

JEL Codes: I11, L83, C80

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1.Introduction

Health tourism is a phenomenon defined by individuals travelling outside their place of residence to maintain, improve or treat their health, and its historical origins date back to ancient times. Today, the phenomenon has become more systematic and diversified due to technological developments, increased transportation and differences in global health systems (Turganbeyeva et al., 2020). This diversification has led to the emergence of "Third Age Tourism". This is a sub-sector of tourism that responds to the expectations of older people in terms of health, leisure and social interaction, and includes both therapeutic and wellness services.

The World Health Organisation (WHO) has introduced the concept of "active ageing" in response to the growing elderly population and related demographic changes in the 21st century. This concept represents a holistic approach to improving the quality of life of older people, encompassing health, social participation and safe environmental conditions (Who, 2002). Active ageing prioritises not only physical health but also psychological and social well-being. In this context, travel is not only a leisure activity for older people, but also a tool that reduces social isolation, increases psychosocial well-being and contributes to life satisfaction (Hung & Lu, 2016).

Research shows that older adults are more likely to be motivated to take part in activities that make a positive contribution to their physical and mental health (Patterson & Balderas, 2020). This trend reflects a conscious decision by older adults to protect their health and maintain their quality of life. In the context of Third Age Tourism, older tourists' expectations and satisfaction with health services are closely related to their overall travel experience. Quality medical care, personalised services and environmental conditions that support recovery are among the key determinants of this satisfaction (Kazerooni et al., 2019).

Today, older travellers tend to benefit not only from traditional healthcare services, but also from holistic practices such as yoga, meditation and healthy eating that promote wellness. In addition, advances in telemedicine practices allow older adults to access healthcare professionals remotely while travelling, supporting a safe travel experience (Carrera, 2025). However, despite all these positive developments, the main barriers that negatively affect older people's travel experience remain problems in accessing health services, variations in service quality and complex structures related to health insurance (Patterson et al., 2021). The need for the sector to move towards more inclusive and age-friendly practices is demonstrated by the inadequacy of services specifically designed for the demographic characteristics of older tourists.

The main objective of this study is to contribute to the systematic analysis of the academic literature focusing on health services and the satisfaction of elderly tourists in the context of Third Age Tourism. In this context, studies published in the Web of Science (WoS) database in the field of health tourism were analysed using the bibliometric analysis method. The research aims to identify the main trends, conceptual relationships and priority research themes in the literature; the data obtained will be presented through network visualisations using scientific mapping techniques. The aim is to develop a holistic perspective that can guide future studies by revealing the structural characteristics of knowledge in the field.

2.Method

2.1.Research Methodology

The bibliometric method of analysis was used in this study. Bibliometric research focuses on network analysis, which examines the relationships between academic elements such as documents, keywords, authors and journals. Mapping and clustering techniques are among the most commonly used methods in this context. These techniques contribute to understanding the diffusion of scientific knowledge and interaction networks by revealing the structural characteristics of the analysed network.

These techniques are used to find answers to the following questions: What are the main research areas and topics within a given scientific discipline? What are the relationships between these fields and topics? How does the discipline develop and change over time? (Waltman et al., 2010). Bibliometric analysis systematically examines the social and structural relationships between different components, such as authors, countries, institutions and research topics, to reveal the bibliometric and intellectual structure of a given field (Donthu et al., 2021).

2.2.Data Collection Method

The data used in the study were obtained by searching the Web of Science (WoS) database on 15 March 2025. For the identified research areas, a literature search was conducted using the keywords ("older tourists" and "health services" and "expectations" or "satisfaction") and ("health tourism" or "medical tourism") in the title and abstract sections, and related studies were listed.

A total of 125 publications were identified. These publications include 98 articles, 12 conference papers, 12 conference reviews, 3 editorials, 1 book and 1 retracted article.

It was found that the first publication on health services and elderly tourists' satisfaction in

tourism for the elderly was published in 2010 and the last publication was published in March 2025. According to the data obtained, the distribution of the studies by years, the citation analysis, the countries where the studies were carried out, the institutions that carried out the research and the organisations that provided the most funding were examined in detail.

2.3.Statistics

VOSviewer 1.6.18 and Microsoft Excel were used for data analysis. Accordingly, journal, author, institution and document-based citation analyses, inter-institutional co-author analyses and inter-author co-citation analyses were performed. While clustering, density and mapping analyses were performed using the VOSviewer software, Microsoft Excel was used to generate tables and graphs showing frequency and percentage distributions of the data. In the evaluation phase, the colours of the elements in the "overlay visualisation" analysis were determined according to the score of each element. By default, blue represents the lowest score, green the medium score and yellow the highest score. In the "network visualisation" analysis, as the weight of an element increases, the size of the circle and label for that element increases proportionally. Similarly, as the strength of the connection between two elements increases, so does the thickness of the lines representing that connection (Eck & Waltman, 2022).

2.4.Ethics

This study does not require ethics committee approval as it only involves the analysis of available data from published articles. Scientific ethical principles were considered during the research process, and compliance with ethical rules was ensured at all stages of the study.

2.5.Findings

Searching the WOS database for the terms ("elderly tourists" AND "health services" AND "expectations" OR "satisfaction") and ("health tourism" or "medical tourism") by searching the specified fields (title, abstract,), it was found that the first study published in WOS on this topic, entitled "A study of the relationship among experiential marketing, experiential value and customer satisfaction", was published in 2010.

It was noted that the most intensive year of studies published in the field of health services and elderly tourist satisfaction in third age tourism was 2022, and it was noted that 15 papers (f = 15) were published in this year. In March 2025, 2 publications were added to the literature. Figure 1 shows the distribution of studies published in this field by year, and a

clear upward trend in the number of publications can be observed in recent years.

Figure 1. Distribution of publications by year

2.6.Keyword Analysis

The keyword analysis in this study is shown in Figure 2. The network map of the keywords used together was created using the "co-occurrence analysis" method, and the "author keywords" option was used as the basis for the analysis. The minimum number of keyword repetitions was set to 5 and accordingly 7 related keywords out of 396 keywords were analysed in detail.

As a result of the analysis, the top five most frequently used keywords are "medical tourism" (f=156), "health tourism" (f=17), "patient satisfaction" (f=13), "service quality" (f=11) and "satisfaction" (f=10). The keywords shown in yellow in the figure represent the most recent keywords in the respective field. (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Keyword network map

2.7. Work Citation Analysis

A density visualisation analysis was performed using the "citations" and "documents" options to determine which publications in the Web of Science (WoS) database were cited by studies on health services and elderly tourist satisfaction in third age tourism. In the analysis process, the minimum number of citations per document was set at 25 and 21 publications that met this criterion were analysed. According to the results of the analysis presented in Figure 3, it can be observed that the most cited works are located in the yellow coloured areas, in accordance with the citation network analysis.

In the analysis, the top five most cited works were identified as. (Han & Hyun, 2015) (f=362), (Suess et al., 2018) (f=109), (Wu et al., 2016) (f=83) ve (Alsharif et al., 2010) (f=70), (Jaapar et al., 2017) (f=61) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Publication citation analysis network map

2.8. Countries Studied

In order to examine the studies on health services and satisfaction of older tourists in tourism for the elderly at the country level, an "overlay visualisation" analysis was applied, using the "bibliographic coupling" and "countries" options. In the analysis process, the minimum number of publications for each country was set at "5" and the minimum number of citations was set at "5". Of the 40 countries that met these criteria, data from 19 countries selected by the software were included in the analysis. The results are shown in Figure 4. According to the results of the analysis, the countries with the highest number of publications are Malaysia (f=25), the United States (f=18), South Korea (f=14), Iran (f=10) and India (f=10).

When analysing the network map of countries, it was found that the highest number of studies was conducted in Malaysia, while the countries with the lowest number of studies were Saudi Arabia, Turkey, Spain, Portugal and Russia (f=5 for each). It was observed that India, one of the most prominent countries in the field of health tourism on a global scale, ranked fourth in terms of number of publications. Furthermore, according to the network map analysis, South Korea ranked first in terms of citation density (f=551) and Indonesia ranked last (f=6).

Figure 4. Distribution of publications by country

2.9. Research Organisations

In order to analyze the institutions conducting research on health services and elderly tourist satisfaction within the scope of third age tourism, “overlay visualization” analysis was performed using “bibliographic coupling” and “organizations” options.

When the minimum number of publications per country was set as “3” and the number of citations as “3”, 12 organizations that met these criteria were identified among a total of 219 organizations and the analysis was carried out on these organizations. The findings of the analysis are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Institutions carrying out the most research

Organization	Number of Articles	Number of Citation	Total Connection Power
University Sains Malasia	5	32	207
University Malaya	4	167	339
Taylors University	4	67	307
University Pannonia	4	26	12
Ucsi University	3	104	341
University Tunku Abdul Rahman	3	103	270
Sojong University	3	408	205
Hanyang University	3	32	198
Islamic Azad University	3	26	107

International Islamic University Malaysia	3	101	81
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Table 2. Top funding agencies

Queue	Funding agencies	Number of grants (n=28)	%
1.	Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT),	2	1,60
2.	Konkuk University	2	1,60
3.	Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University (PNU)	2	1,60
4.	Anhui Provincial Key Research and Development Plan	1	0,80
5.	Canada Research Chairs (CRC)	1	0,80

2.10.Discussion

Although there are many studies on health tourism in the literature, the number of bibliometric analyses focusing on health services and elderly tourist satisfaction in the context of third age tourism among the works published in the Web of Science (WoS) database is rather limited. This study is a comprehensive analysis of the publications in the WoS database using the VOSviewer software in terms of the distribution of publications by years, citation analysis, countries where the research was carried out, institutions that carried out the research and organisations that provided the most funding.

In this study it was found that the most frequently used keywords in the literature on health services and satisfaction of elderly tourists in the context of tourism for the elderly are "medical tourism" (f=156), "health tourism" (f=17), "patient satisfaction" (f=13), "service quality" (f=11) and "satisfaction" (f=10). When the studies on health tourism are evaluated from a holistic perspective, although the keyword "health tourism" is expected, it can be seen that the term "medical tourism", which is a subcategory of health tourism, is preferred in the majority of studies. The reason for this situation is that the studies on the elderly are carried out with a focus on satisfaction with health services and in this context it is assumed that the studies on the elderly receiving health services are mainly dealt with in the context of medical tourism.

Looking at the studies conducted in the field of health services and satisfaction of elderly tourists in the context of third age tourism, it can be seen that Han & Hyun (2015) "Customer retention in the medical tourism industry: Impact of quality, satisfaction, trust, and price reasonableness" is the most cited publication (f=362).

Suess et.al., (2028) "Perceived impacts of medical tourism development on community

wellbeing" is the second most cited paper (f=109). These studies are followed by Wu et.al. (2016) "A Study of Behavioural Intentions, Patient Satisfaction, Perceived Value, Patient Trust and Experiential Quality for Medical Tourists" (f=83), Alsharif et.al. (2010) "Patients beyond borders: A study of medical tourists in four countries" (f=70) and Jaapar et.al. (2017) "Dental tourism: Examining tourist profiles, motivation and satisfaction" (f=61). The first published paper is "A Study of the Relationship among Experiential Marketing, Experiential Value and Customer Satisfaction" by Chan & Hsieh (2010). This is one of the least cited studies, with a total of seven citations (f=7).

It can be seen that the most cited studies were not the first works in the literature; in particular, the studies published in 2015 and 2018 contributed more to the field. In this sense, it can be said that the most cited works in the literature stand out according to factors such as the level of originality, scientific quality and the qualities they carry, and therefore receive higher citation levels. Although it was found that 'University Sains Malaysia' was the institution that conducted the most research in the field of health tourism, it was found that the most cited study was conducted by 'Sojong University'. This shows that the high number of publications is not directly related to the high number of citations. The results show that the number of citations is more related to the quality, originality and scientific merit of the study.

Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT), Konkuk University and Princess Nourah Bint Abdulrahman University were found to be the organizations that provided the most funding support for the studies.

While the country with the highest number of research institutions is Malaysia, the organization providing funding support to the highest number of publications is Portugal. The analysis revealed that the funding support provided during the publication process does not have a direct significant effect on the institutions that publish

3.Conclusion

The study of studies published in the Web of Science (WoS) database in the field of health services and the satisfaction of elderly tourists in the context of Third Age Tourism has allowed a bibliometric evaluation of the subject. The importance of health tourism is increasing day by day, as is the number of scientific publications on the subject. As a result of the evaluation, it has been determined which countries have published in the field of elderly tourist satisfaction and health services; it has been determined that the most research in this field has been carried out by Malaysia and the United States, and that the most publishing institutions are located in Malaysia. It has been concluded that the majority of the countries in the top 10 in health tourism do not publish or support such studies on health

services and elderly tourist satisfaction within the scope of third age tourism. The analysis reveals that the studies in this field are inadequate, and researchers who plan to conduct research in this field are recommended to publish on related topics.

In addition, researchers who wish to publish academic papers can apply to the relevant funding programmes to obtain funding for their studies and ensure that their research findings are published in international peer-reviewed journals. In addition to contributing to the literature in the field of health tourism, the results will serve as a qualified reference source for further scientific research and strategic planning in the field.

Declaration of Research and Publication Ethics

This study which does not require ethics committee approval and/or legal/specific permission complies with the research and publication ethics.

Researcher's Contribution Rate Statement

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article.

Declaration of Researcher's Conflict of Interest

There is no potential conflicts of interest in this study.

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